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CORRELATION BETWEEN SERUM ZINC, INSULIN AND C-PEPTIDE IN PATIENTS OF TYPE 2 DM IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN NORTH INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Zinc has been reported to be involved in the synthesis and release of insulin and C-peptide from the beta cells of pancreas. The possibility of a correlation between these parameters needs to be explored, specially with regards diabetes mellitus. We aimed at analysing this relationship in the Indian population by measuring the serum levels of Insulin, C-peptide and zinc in type 2 diabetics. A cross sectional study was undertaken on hundred type 2 diabetic patients in a tertiary hospital (MMIMSR) in North India. Serum C-peptide, insulin were measured by chemiluminescence immunoassay and zinc by spectrophotometry. We found that serum C-peptide and insulin levels were raised (2.59 ± 1.45 ng/ml, 11.24 ± 10.57 μ IU/ml respectively) while serum zinc levels were within reference intervals (97.82 ± 11.27 μ g/dl). Zinc levels however showed highly significant negative correlations with serum C-peptide ($r=0.649$, $p<0.001$) and insulin ($r= -0.423$, $p< 0.001$) levels. We conclude that serum zinc levels are strongly relate to serum insulin and c-peptide levels in patients of type 2 DM and may thus have a role in the pathogenesis and hence treatment of the disease.

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INTRODUCTION

Type 2 DM, which was until recently considered to be a disease of the rich countries, is now emerging in epidemic proportions in the developing countries [1]. 72.1 million people, which is about 1/6th of all the adults with diabetes in the world, live in India. The number is expected to rise to 134.3 million in 2045 [2]. Significantly raised levels of insulin have been reported in type 2 diabetics in some studies [3,4]. Recent studies have also shown that C-peptide, a co product of insulin secretion, is a biologically active peptide with a host of physiological roles [5,6,7]. Raised C-peptide levels have been reported in diabetics in some studies [8,9]. Zinc, one of the most important trace elements in our body, is required for multiple steps in insulin synthesis, release and action [10,11]. Estimation of serum zinc levels in diabetic patients has yielded varying results with some authors like Basaki et al and Al-Marouf et al reporting decreased levels while Zargar et al reporting normal levels and Fujimoto et al reporting raised levels [12-15]. With the above background, the current study was planned. Serum insulin, c-peptide zinc levels were estimated in North Indian type 2 diabetic patients. The objective was to see if there was a relationship between the serum levels of these parameters which could then be explored for therapeutic benefit.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the Departments of Biochemistry and General Medicine, Maharishi Markandeshwar Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Mullana, Ambala, Haryana on hundred type 2 diabetic patients admitted in the Department of General Medicine /attending the Medical OPD. Prediagnosed diabetic patients, >30 yrs of age, were chosen for the study. Subjects with Type 1 DM, patients receiving insulin, supplements or medications containing zinc (multi vitamins etc), pregnant and lactating women and patients with thyroid dysfunction were excluded from the study. Patients were selected randomly. DM was defined according to the American Diabetic Association (ADA) guidelines [16], which are as under:

- HbA1C >6.5%. OR
- FPG >126 mg/dL (>7.0 mmol/L). (Fasting = no caloric intake for at least 8 h.)*OR
- 2-h plasma glucose >200mg/dL (>11.1mmol/L). OR
- In a patient with classic symptoms of hyperglycemia or hyperglycemic crisis, a random plasma glucose >200 mg/dl (>11.1 mmol/L).

Clinical data

Demographic and clinical data were collected with the help of a self designed, pretested questionnaire.

Sample collection and transport

For accurate comparison to established normal values, fasting morning serum samples were obtained after an overnight fast of at least 8 hrs. The blood was collected aseptically, preferably from antecubital vein in a plain red-top venipuncture tube containing clot activator (*BDTM VacutainerTM*) (without anticoagulants or gel barrier). Care was taken to ensure that no hemolysis took place during or after sample collection. The samples were allowed to clot for 30-60 minutes at room temperature. This was followed by centrifugation using *RemiTM R-23* research centrifuge. Serum was then separated and aliquots were made. Serum C-peptide, insulin, fasting blood glucose and zinc levels were then measured. Samples that required storage for upto 5 days were kept under refrigeration at 2-8°C. Samples that required storage for longer periods (upto 30 days) were stored at -40°C in deep freezer (*RemiTM Ultra Low Freezer*).

Quantitative assays

Estimation of serum insulin and C-peptide levels was done by Chemiluminescence immunoassay technique on *AutoplexTM CLIA* (chemiluminescence immunoassay) workstation using *AcculiteTM* C-peptide and Insulin test kits (*MonobindTM Inc.(US)*).

Estimation of zinc was done by Colorimetric method on *Pace plusTM* semi auto analyser using *CoralTM* zinc kit. Fasting blood glucose was estimated by Trinders method (GOD-POD) on *Pace plusTM* semi auto analyser using *Erba glucose kit* (*Erba diagnostics Mannheim, Germany*). The serum samples were analysed for glucose levels within 2 hrs of sample collection.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS and Microsoft Excel. Descriptive analysis was performed, followed by graphical representation of different parameters in terms of mean / median and standard deviation / range. Patients were grouped on basis of age, BMI and duration of DM. Since many parameters like insulin, C-peptide, did not follow a Gaussian distribution, log transformation was performed on these parameters to normalize the distribution, as has been reported in several other studies [17-21]. Pearson's coefficient was used to analyse the different parameters for correlation and student t test was performed to analyse the hypertensive and normotensive patients for association. P value <0.05 was considered significant.

Ethical justification

Ethical approval was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of the institute on the agreement that patient anonymity must be maintained, good laboratory practice, quality control ensured, and that every finding will be treated with utmost confidentiality and for the purpose of this research only.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics:

We found that serum insulin levels were raised in diabetic patients. Mean insulin levels were 11.24 ± 10.57 $\mu\text{IU/ml}$ (reference interval = 0-10 $\mu\text{IU/ml}$). Median, interquartile range and SEM were 7.1, 3.98-13.35 and 1.06 $\mu\text{IU/ml}$ respectively. Similar results were reported by Gayoso-diz et al (2013) and Islam et al (2013) [22, 23]. The raised serum insulin levels can be attributed to the fact that type 2 diabetes mellitus primarily involves insulin resistance (unlike type 1 where decreased insulin secretion is the main defect). To overcome this resistance, β cells of pancreas increase the synthesis and release of insulin, thereby leading to hyperinsulinemia.

In our study, we observed that serum C-peptide levels were also raised in diabetic patients 2.59 ± 1.45 ng/ml (reference interval = 0.78-1.89 ng/ml) Median, interquartile range and SEM were 2.00, 1.6-3.7 and 0.15 ng/ml respectively. Similar findings were reported by Kim et al (2011) and Chowta et al (2010) [8,9]. The elevation of C-peptide levels can be explained by the fact that it is produced in equimolar amounts by β cells of pancreas along with insulin by splitting of the common precursor, proinsulin. In patients with type 2 DM, the compensatory increase in C-peptide levels is attributed to the increased rate of synthesis and release of its precursor, proinsulin in an effort to reverse the hyperglycemia seen in the disease. Proinsulin, after release, splits into insulin and C-peptide.

In our study, we found that serum zinc levels were within reference intervals in diabetic patients. Mean values were 97.82 ± 11.27 $\mu\text{g/dl}$ (reference interval = 80-120 $\mu\text{g/dl}$). Median, interquartile range and SEM were 96.9, 89.55-108 and 1.13 $\mu\text{g/dl}$ respectively (Fig 1). Zargar et al (1998) reported slightly raised zinc levels of 112 ± 32.13 $\mu\text{g/dl}$ (17.19 ± 4.92 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) [14]. In other studies, however, many different types of relationships have been reported between diabetes mellitus and serum zinc levels [24,15]. Decreased levels of serum zinc were reported in type 2 diabetic patients by Parham et al (2008) (76 ± 16 $\mu\text{g/dl}$) [25], Ferdousi et al (2012) (72.70 ± 8.43 $\mu\text{g/dl}$) [26] and Al-Marooof et al (2006) (68.9 ± 11.9 mg/dl) [13]. On the other hand, Fujimoto et al (1986) reported increased zinc levels have been found in patients with diabetes mellitus previously treated with insulin [15]. Similarly Rusu et al (2005) reported raised zinc levels in type 2 diabetics [27]. These differences could be at least partly due to heterogeneity in patient selection, study design and method of detection of serum zinc levels.

In our study we found no significant difference in the zinc levels in males and females (98.65 ± 11.15 in females and 97.30 ± 11.41 in males) ($p=0.562$). Saharia et al (2013) in their study on newly diagnosed type 2 DM cases observed that the mean serum zinc concentration was 80.83 ± 13.1 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ in case of males and 77.56 ± 14.2 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ in case of females. The difference was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$) [28]. Masood et al (2009) also reported similar insignificant gender difference in zinc levels ($p=0.10$) [24].

Figure 1: Median and interquartile range of fasting serum zinc levels.

Correlations:

A strong positive correlation was observed between (log) insulin and (log) C-peptide levels. The correlation was statistically highly significant ($r=0.649$, $p=0.000$). This strong correlation can in part be attributed to the fact that insulin and C-peptide are released in equimolar amounts from beta cells of pancreas. Because fasting C-peptide levels are 5 -10 % higher than those of insulin owing to a longer half life of C-Peptide, and because unlike insulin, C-peptide does not undergo first pass metabolism in liver and its concentration is not affected by interference from insulin antibodies often present in patients receiving insulin therapy, many authors have proposed the use of C-peptide as a surrogate marker insulin release and β cell function [7,29].

A strong negative correlation was found between serum zinc and (log) insulin levels. The correlation was highly significant ($r= -0.423$, $p<0.001$) (fig 2)

Figure 2: Correlation between fasting serum zinc levels ($\mu\text{g/dl}$) and (log) serum insulin.

A strong negative correlation was found between serum zinc and (log) C-peptide levels. The correlation was highly significant ($r = -0.518$, $p < 0.001$) (fig 3). These negative correlations can probably be explained by the biochemical role played by zinc in insulin release and action. Zinc is known to increase the sensitivity of insulin by several mechanisms. Zinc facilitates hexamerisation and crystal formation of insulin, processes which been suggested that crystal formation increases the degree of conversion of soluble pro-insulin to insoluble insulin [30]. Several other modes of action have been described to explain the improved action of insulin by Zinc. It appears that Zinc can have direct insulin-like effects, which may be due to inhibition of the important glycogen-regulating enzyme GSK3. Other mechanisms include stimulation of the postreceptor proteins Akt and PI3-kinase. Zn can also reduce cytokines such as IL- 1β as well as NF κ B. Zn induces metallothionein synthesis, whereby Zn may have indirect efficacy. [30-32]. All these proposed mechanisms can lead to increased insulin sensitivity (and decreased insulin resistance). In view of the improved sensitivity of insulin, its release by β cells will be decreased. Thus, serum levels of insulin, C-peptide as well as β cell activity will be less if zinc levels are more and vice versa.

Figure 3: Correlation between fasting serum zinc levels ($\mu\text{g/dl}$) and (log) serum C-peptide.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In our study we found highly significant correlations between serum levels of zinc, C-peptide and insulin in patients of type 2 DM. While Serum levels of zinc were within reference intervals, those of insulin and C-peptide were raised in patients of type 2 DM. Given the fact that insulin and c-peptide are fundamental to the origins of type 2 DM, the strong negative correlation that zinc shares with these parameters points out towards a possible role of zinc in the pathogenesis of the disease. Large scale collaborated studies with a wider patient base are required to through further light on the subject. Further, therapeutic trials evaluating this role a need of the hour.

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AUTHOR STATEMENTS

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical issues

The study was done after obtaining proper ethical approval by the Institutional Ethics Committee of MMIMSR.

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